

DECOLONIZATION OF ECONOMICS EDUCATION FOR SUSTAINABLE CREATIVITY AND HUMAN CAPITAL DEVELOPMENT IN PUBLIC UNIVERSITIES IN RIVERS STATE

BY

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20976759>

Abstract

This study examined decolonization of economics education for sustainable creativity and human capital development in public universities in Rivers State. Two research questions and two hypotheses guided the study which adopted descriptive survey design. The three public universities offering economics education and the 360 economics education lecturers in these institutions formed the population of the study. The sample size of 108 lecturers (67 male and 41 females) was drawn through the stratified random sampling method. A questionnaire titled, “Decolonization of Economics Education for Sustainable Creativity and Human Capital Development Questionnaire (DEESCHCDQ)” was used for data collection. The instrument was adequately validated. An overall reliability index of 0.89 was obtained using Cronbach Alpha method. Mean scores and standard deviation were used to analyze the research questions, while z-test was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The results of the study showed that, ways of decolonizing economics education for sustainable creativity and human capital development include among others: Contextualization of the curriculum; blending indigenous knowledge system with Western curriculum; and use of instructional resources rooted to students socio-cultural background. The hinderances to decolonization of economics education as revealed by the study include among others; inability of economics education curriculum planners to adequately contextualize it and blend IKS with Western curriculum; inadequate funding of education; and high influence of western culture and technology on developing countries. Based on the findings, conclusion was drawn and the following recommendations among others were made: curriculum of economics education should be adequately contextualized; and government should demonstrate the political will to effectively implement policy frameworks aimed at decolonizing economics education.

Keywords: Decolonization, Economics Education, Sustainable Creativity, Human Capital Development, Public Universities

Introduction

With enormous human and material resources, Nigeria remains the poverty capital of the world. According to World Bank (2025), poverty rate among rural Nigerians has risen up to 75%, and approximately 63% of Nigerians are living in multidimensional poverty. This figure represents a surge from previous years and it is driven by high inflation, currency devaluation, and economic reforms. The question that has remained unanswered over time is, “What are the root causes of this multidimensional endemic

poverty, rocking Nigeria, and what can we do to lift Nigeria out of this ugly situation?” the quest for development is a global one hence, the United Nations (UN) took up the challenge of formulating and adopting seventeen (17) sustainable development goals (SDGs) in January, 2016. Progress towards the attainment of SDGs will greatly depend on functional education, rooted in the culture of the people. Consequently, Nigerian development can only be possible if its education evolves from the culture of the people. Indigenous education fosters cultural

preservation, character training, and community unity by passing down traditional knowledge through observations and storytelling.

Indigenous education promotes practical, vocational skills for self-reliance, functionalism, and deep respect for elders. It was noted for its advantages such as: cultural preservation and identity; character development and morality; functionalism and practical skills; community cohesion and social responsibility; environmental stewardship; and holistic learning. These values and indigenous identity have been eroded away due to colonization by the Europeans. Africans and Nigerians in particular, currently suffer from mental slavery. They have inferiority complex, and suffer from loss of confidence to conquer and rule their world due to negative impacts of colonialism and imperialism. Nigerians now believe that, whatsoever that comes from the white man is the best and superior to anything tagged Nigerian. Hence, the rush for foreign goods and the neglect for locally made goods. This scenario has impacted into all areas of our life and economy; our educational system is currently dominated with foreign ideas, culture and technology. There is little or no consideration for our indigenous values, culture and technology in our educational system. This situation has impacted negatively into our moral lives, economic and social development. It has increased our poverty rate tremendously from what it was before colonization. We have lost our identity in almost all areas of our life. This mental slavery needs to be corrected.

There is an urgent need of emancipation from this ugly trend through decolonization. Decolonization according to Obiagbaosogu and Nwosu (2025) is a process of deconstruction and reconstruction of the minds of Africans. Adebisi (2016) sees colonization as nothing but an enterprise of appropriation,

familiarization and utilization meant to silence African history, knowledge and autonomy. According to Adebisi (2016), to control the human mind, the colonial masters needed to have control over the education of the colonies. This is because education is believed to have revolutionary capacities and could be used to change the course of history. This is why educational models used in Africa especially in Nigeria should emphasize critical thinking/reasoning and originality wherein Knowledge is put to test and the individuals queries even the content of his knowledge. No wonder Freire in Adebisi (2016) states that:

No pedagogy which is truly liberating can remain distant from the oppressed by treating them as unfortunates and by presenting for their emulation models from among the oppressors. The oppressed must be their own example in the struggle for their redemption (p. 44)

Freire is suggesting a rethink in Nigeria's educational system to fit local needs, not just copying Western Models. Decolonization of education especially economics education in this case is all about; local focus where we teach Nigeria's economy, agriculture, technology, and culture; practical skills where we equip students for local job markets (entrepreneurship, farming, trades etc); cultural relevance where local values are blended with global trends; and self-sufficiency where there is less dependency on

foreign ideas, goods, lifestyle, and local innovations is given a boost.

Decolonizing economics education in public universities in Rivers State implies replacing eurocentric models of economics education with indigenous knowledge systems (IKS) and local contexts to foster sustainable creativity and relevant human capital development. By integrating local economic realities, such as sustainable agriculture, or the informal sector, into the curriculum, universities can better prepare graduates to solve regional challenges, ultimately enhancing both human capital development and sustainable economic growth. Sustainable creativity means generating innovative ideas that meet current needs without compromising future potential. It is about fostering innovation, adapting to change and promotion of long-term impact so that it will be beneficial to future generations. Human capital development on the other hand has to do with investing in people through education, training, and healthcare to enhance the acquisition of relevant skills, productivity, economic growth, and personal development. Public universities are universities that are established and funded by the government. In Rivers State, there are three public universities namely: University of Port Harcourt, Rivers State University; and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education. All the three universities offer economics education as part of their programs. The effort in this paper is directed towards investigating how we can decolonize economics education to enhance sustainable creativity and human capital development in public universities in Rivers State.

Statement of the Problem

Economics education as a program in public universities in Rivers State is dominated with colonial – era curricula contexts, which focuses more on western perspectives. It has little or limited local contexts. This situation

potentially hinders sustainable creativity and human capital development in a rapidly evolving global economy especially in developing countries. There is the need to investigate how economics education can be decolonized to foster creativity, innovation, and equip students with skills relevant in solving local and global challenges. Decolonizing economics education program implies reorienting curricula, teaching methods, and research towards local contexts, leveraging Rivers State rich cultural heritage, natural resources, and entrepreneurial spirit. By aligning education with local needs and potentials, public universities in Rivers State can drive sustainable creativity, human capital development, and economic growth. Therefore, the problem of this study is to investigate ways we can decolonize economics education program in public universities in Rivers State for sustainable creativity and human capital development.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study is to investigate decolonization of economics education for sustainable creativity and human capital development in public universities in Rivers State. Specifically, the objectives of this study were to;

1. Examine ways of decolonizing economics education for sustainable creativity and human capital development in public universities in Rivers State.
2. Ascertain the challenges of decolonizing economics education for sustainable creativity and human capital development in public universities in Rivers State

Research Questions

The following research questions were answered in this study:

1. In what ways can we decolonize economics education for sustainable creativity and human capital

development in public universities in Rivers State?

2. What are the challenges of decolonization of economics education for sustainable creativity and human capital development in public universities in Rivers State?

Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant difference between the mean responses of male and female economics education lecturers in public universities in Rivers State, on ways we can decolonize economics education for sustainable creativity and human capital development in public universities in Rivers State.
2. There is no significant difference between the mean responses of male and female economics education lecturers in public universities in Rivers State on the challenges of decolonization of economics education for sustainable creativity and human capital development in public universities in Rivers State.

Literature Review

Any education that is not productivity oriented is mere rhetoric (Obiagbaosogu & Nwosu, 2024). Africa needs more of skills and career-oriented education to enable her contribute to world civilization. A review of Africa's precolonial history presents rural communities where moonlight stories and plays, that aided knowledge and culture transmission, and learning about our ancestors and heroes past were told. This oral traditional education of telling generational legends in the humid moonlight helped to preserve a sense of community, connectivity and continuity. Education frameworks in Africa must be modelled or domesticated toward creating a new and authentic model of education that will enable them solve their indigenous problems.

Higher education according to Lazarus, Zhang, Shitu, Wang, and Issifu (2025) is undergoing a transformative process of decolonization aimed at reforming curricula, integrating indigenous knowledge system, and promoting educational serenity to better severe the divers cultural, social and economic needs of global citizens. This process seeks to dismantle the colonial legacies embedded in educational systems and create a more inclusive and equitable learning environment.

By embracing indigenous perspectives and knowledge systems, education institutions can provide more culturally relevant and socially equitable education. According to Ndiouva-Gatsheim (2017), decolonized education prioritizes locally produced knowledge, contextual competence, and contribute to socio-economic development. It seeks cognitive justice by expanding beyond Western education frameworks, incorporating diverse learning approaches from marginalized communities. Decolonization, as presented in this article, does not reject western knowledge but rather calls for the inclusion of Nigerian ideologies to promote educational relevance. The challenge is the dominance of Euro-centric knowledge and methods of education which has resulted to the marginalization of indigenous knowledge and cultures (Santos, 2014).

In the context of decolonization, this article emphasizes introduction of experiences and knowledge structures that are indigenous to the students which would enhance their understanding and application of economic concepts. It will involve contextualizing curriculum to incorporate African perspectives, Nigerian case studies, and local economic realities. Corroborating this idea, Sani and Ikpe (2014) stated that, education plays a critical role in the development of the society especially, through its development of needed structures, the manpower required for

social and technological advancement of the society the manpower therefore, cannot achieve the objective of developing the society through the implementation of foreign ideologies. Consequently, the education and training of the needed manpower to advance Africa's development must incorporate elements of the African knowledge structures, with a focus on the challenges faced within the African social and cultural contexts.

Recognizing the socio-cultural aspects of knowledge acquisition showcases the need for alternative approaches to instruction delivery. There is the need to integrate the distinct indigenous knowledge system (IKS) into the formal classroom activities as a means of enhancing students' conceptualization. According to Ayeni (2021), this may require adaptive expertise as a requisite skill for the successful integration of IKS. Integrating IKS requires blending traditional economic practices with modern theories. Supporting contextualization of curriculum and the integration of IKS, Letsekha (2013) was of the view that, African education must equip youth with problem-solving skills, cultural identity, and a balance between local and global perspectives in a rapidly changing world.

African scholars should be encouraged to question western-centric models and innovate solutions for local challenges. This would require targeted teacher professional development (TPD) programs. These programmes would prepare teachers to navigate the epistemological differences and overlaps between Western curriculum and IKS, enabling them to develop instructional materials grounded in students' socio-cultural contexts. Such resources must be developed locally, with sensitivity to the specific cultural and environmental knowledge that students bring to the classroom. They should encourage students to question Western-centric curriculum, emphasize entrepreneurship, local

resource management, community engagement, and critical thinking (Atiku, Kankia & Abdulkadia, 2025; Adeyemi, 2012).

Suggesting curriculum overhaul as a strategy for decolonizing economics education in higher institutions, Major and Leigha (2019) recommended the inclusion of Nigerian economic history, informal sector studies, and local resource management. They advocated for the use of textbooks written by African economists in Nigerian educational system. Renowned African economists and successful business entrepreneurs could be invited as guest speakers or lecturers from time to time to motivate the students and promote decolonization of economics education. Corroborating their view, Bassey (2001) opined that entrepreneurship integration is very necessary and demands offering causes on local entrepreneurship, innovation, and business incubation. It will require students being linked with local industries for internship and mentorship.

Decolonization of education in Nigeria according to Adebayo (2018) and Onyekwelu (2020) would require community engagement. Educational institutions would be required to partner with local businesses, non-governmental organizations and communities for project-based learning in other to enhance indigenization of economics education and the capacity of students to solve real local challenges. Also, Scholars like Mavuru and Makhunga (2020) have explained the need for continuous professional development (CPD) of teachers and the training of teachers on decolonization of pedagogical strategies and the integration of local system knowledge in education contexts. The incorporation of indigenous research frameworks in higher education can promote values such as multilogicality, coexistence of multiple knowledge systems and rationality, thus encouraging equitable practice in research,

teaching, and mentoring (Reano, 2020). Promoting educational sovereignty through decolonial professional development and intercultural dialogue is essential for valuing indigenous students' cultural resources and integrating their socio-cultural practices and languages into their academic settings (Alvarez- Valencia & Valencia, 2023).

Decolonization of economics education at the university level will promote students capacity to solve economic challenges rooted in local contexts. Despite the numerous benefits and potentials decolonization of economics education stands to offer, it is confronted by numerous challenges. Obaizamomwan (2024) listed and explained the obstacles faced by economics education as: unprofessionally published textbooks; inadequate instructors; inadequate research funding; underutilization of information and communication technology; and inadequate development of skills in economics instruction. Abiola and Samuel (2023) identified the challenges of curriculum decolonization in Nigeria as shortage of qualified/skilled personnel, corruption, tribalism/ nepotism, administrative inconsistencies, poor facilities, politicization of educational decisions, Decolonization of economics education equally faces the inability of curriculum planners to formulate curriculum that accommodate traditional economic practices and values of immediate community and Western curriculum adequately. The pedagogical approaches, especially the language of instruction. According to Ocho (2013) being unable to effectively use indigenous language alongside English language as language of instruction in our educational system up to university level is a challenge to decolonization of our educational system.

Isa and Lawal (2023) identified the challenges of decolonization of economics education as

inadequate infrastructure; limited funding; shortage of qualified/experienced teachers; euro-centric curriculum; and insufficient research and development of indigenous knowledge system hinders decolonization of economics education.

Research Methods

Descriptive survey research design was adopted in this study. The population of the study comprised of the three public universities in Rivers State (University of Port Harcourt, Rivers State University, and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education) offering economics education and the 360 economics education lecturers (224 male and 136 female). A sample of 108 respondents was drawn through stratified random sampling technique (67 male and 41 female). This sample size represented 30% of the population. A questionnaire titled: “Decolonization of Economics Education for Sustainable Creativity and Human Capital DEVELOPMENT Questionnaire (DEESCHCDQ)” was used for data collection. The instrument which contained 18 items structured on four-point Likert rating scale was adequately validated by two lecturers from Educational Management and one from Measurement and Evaluation. An overall reliability index of 0.89 was obtained through Cronbach Alpha method. Mean scores and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions, while z-test was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Research Question One: In what ways can we decolonize economics education for sustainable creativity and human capital development in public universities in Rivers State?

Table 1: Mean scores and standard deviation analysis of the responses of male and female Lecturers on ways economics education can be decolonized for sustainable creativity and human capital development in public universities in Rivers State.

S/N	Ways Economics Education can be Decolonized for Sustainable Creativity and Human Capital Development	Male Lecturers	Female Lecturers		Mean Set	Remarks	
		N = 67 \bar{x}_1	N= 41 \bar{x}_2 SD_2				
1.	Contextualization of the curriculum of economics education.	3.24	1.04	3.22	1.06	3.23	Agree
2.	Blending IKS and traditional economic practices with Western curriculum for economics education.	3.28	1.02	3.14	1.11	3.21	Agree
3.	Use of instructional resources rooted to students socio-cultural contexts in the teaching of economics education.	3.18	1.07	3.20	1.08	3.19	Agree
4.	Community engagement and collaboration to promote the integration of local economic practices/entrepreneurship into the curriculum of economics education.	3.20	1.06	3.12	1.13	3.16	Agree
5.	Incorporation of indigenous research frameworks in the university to promote decolonization of economics education.	3.16	1.08	3.18	1.09	3.17	Agree
6.	Promotion of educational sovereignty.	3.08	1.12	3.10	1.15	3.09	Agree
7.	Pidgin English/indigenous language can be blended with English language during instruction delivery in the universities.	3.12	1.10	3.12	1.13	3.12	Agree
8.	Adequate training and retraining and teachers on pedagogical approaches that will enhance decolonization of economics education in our universities.	3.16	1.03	3.30	0.99	3.28	Agree
9.	Employ foreigners to teach economics education using foreign educational resources in the universities.	2.32	1.14	2.28	1.18	2.30	Disagree
Aggregate mean and standard deviation		3.09	1.07	3.07	1.10		

Criterion mean = 2.50

Table 1 shows that items 1 to 8 had weighted mean scores that are greater than the criterion mean of 2.50 and were accepted as ways economics education can be decolonized for sustainable creativity and human capital development in public universities in Rivers State. item number 9 with weighted mean score of 2.30 was rejected. The aggregate mean of 3.09 and 3.07 for male and female lecturers which did not differ so much revealed that, the

respondents shared similar opinion on ways economics education can be decolonized in public universities in Rivers State.

Therefore, ways economics education can be decolonized for sustainable creativity and human capital development in public universities in Rivers State include: contextualization of the curriculum; blending IKS and traditional economic practices with

western curriculum; use of instructional resources rooted to students socio-cultural backgrounds in teaching economics education; community engagement and collaboration with universities to promote entrepreneurship and local economic practices; incorporation of indigenous research frameworks; blending pidgin English/indigenous delivery; and adequate training/ retraining of teachers on

pedagogical approaches required for decolonization of economics education in public universities in Rivers State.

Research Question Two: What are the challenges of decolonization of economics education for sustainable creativity and human capital development in public universities in Rivers State?

Table 2: Mean scores and standard deviation analysis of the responses of male and female Lecturers on the challenges of decolonization of economics education for sustainable creativity and human, capital development in public universities in Rivers State.

S/N	Challenges of decolonization of economics education in public universities in Rivers State.	Male Lecturers N = 67		Female Lecturers N = 41		Mean Set	Remarks
		\bar{x}_1	SD_1	\bar{x}_2	SD_2		
1.	Inability of curriculum planners in economics education to adequately contextualize it and blend IKS with Western curriculum.	2.86	1.01	2.82	1.07	2.84	Agree
2.	Shortage of qualified curriculum planners in economics education	3.04	0.94	3.02	1.04	3.03	Agree
3.	Infrastructural challenges	3.00	0.96	3.04	1.02	3.02	Agree
4.	Inadequate funding of education	3.08	0.93	3.06	1.01	3.07	Agree
5.	High-influence of Western culture and technology on developing nations.	3.16	0.91	3.08	0.99	3.12	Agree
6.	Insufficient indigenous research frameworks and development of IKS.	3.12	0.92	3.10	0.98	3.11	Agree
7.	Lack of political will to promote decolonization of economics education	3.20	0.89	3.14	0.97	3.17	Agree
8.	Inadequate training and preparation of economics education teachers through decolonization of education professional development and intercultural dialogue.	2.94	0.98	2.96	1.05	2.95	Agree
9.	Unwillingness of university authorities to participate in the process of decolonization of economics education.	2.18	1.06	2.24	1.08	2.21	Disagree
	Aggregate mean and standard deviation	2.95	0.96	2.94	1.02		

Criterion mean = 2.50

Table 2 revealed that, all the items (1-8) had weighted mean scores that are greater than the criterion mean of 2.50 except item number 9. Items 1-8 were accepted while item 9 was rejected. The aggregate mean of 2.95 and 2.94 for male and female lecturers respectively indicate that, the respondents shared a common

opinion on the challenges of decolonization of economics education in public universities in Rivers State.

Therefore, the challenges of decolonization of economics education in public universities in Rivers State include: inability of economics education curriculum planners to adequately

contextualize it and blend IKS with Western curriculum; shortage of qualified curriculum planners in economics education; infrastructural challenges; inadequate funding of education; high influence of western culture and technology on developing countries; insufficient indigenous research frameworks and development of IKS; lack of political will to promote decolonization of economics education; and inadequate training and preparation of economics education teachers through decolonization of education

professional development and intercultural dialogue.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis One: There is no significant difference between the mean responses of male and female economics education lecturers in public universities in Rivers State on ways we can decolonize economics education for sustainable creativity and human capital development in public universities in Rivers State.

Table 3: z-test of difference between the mean scores of male and female economics education lecturers on ways economics education can be decolonized for sustainable creativity and human capital development in public universities in Rivers State.

Gender	N	\bar{X}	SD	Df	z-cal.	z-crit.	Level of Decision sign.	of	Decision
Male Lecturers	67	3.09	1.07					Ho1	not
Female lecturers	41	3.07	0.10	106	0.093	± 1.960	0.05		significant

The result in Table 3 shows that, the mean scores of male and female lecturers stood at 3.09 and 3.07 respectively. These scores appear closely related and did not differ so much from each other. Furthermore, at 106 degrees of freedom and 0.05 level of significance, the calculated z-score of 0.093 is by far less than the z-critical or table value of ± 1.960 . Hence, the researcher could not reject the null hypothesis. Therefore, the researcher established that, there is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female lecturers on ways economics

education can be decolonized for sustainable creativity and human capital development in public universities in Rivers State.

Hypothesis Two: There is no significant difference between the mean responses of male and female economics education lecturers in public universities in Rivers State on the challenges of decolonization of economics education for sustainable creativity and human capital development in public universities in Rivers State.

Table 4: z-test of difference between the mean scores of male and female economics education lecturers on the challenges of decolonization of economics education for sustainable creativity and human capital development in public universities in Rivers State

Gender	N	\bar{X}	SD	Df	z-cal.	z-crit.	Level of Decision sign.	of	Decision
Male Lecturers	67	2.95	0.96					Ho2	not
Female lecturers	41	2.94	1.02	106	0.051	± 1.960	0.05		significant

Results in Table 4 reveal that, the mean scores of male and female lecturers stood at 2.95 and

2.94 respectively. These scores are very close. Furthermore, at 106 degrees of freedom and

0.05 level of significance, the calculated z-score of 0.051 is by far less than the z-critical or table value of ± 1.960 . Hence, the null hypothesis was not rejected but rather, it was retained. The researcher therefore maintained that, there is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female lecturers on the challenges of decolonization of economics education for sustainable creativity and human capital development in public universities in Rivers State.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of the study have revealed some of the ways economics education can be decolonized, which include contextualizing the curriculum and blending IKS and traditional economic practices with Western curriculum. Contextualizing the curriculum implies making it relevant to the students background, bringing in local ideas and economic practices into it. This is necessary because indigenous knowledge is very important as a foundation for the comprehension of modern and advanced knowledge. Situating Western ideas within home grown ideas and cultural contexts of the students will enhance their understanding and sustainable creativity. Supporting this finding, Adebisi (2016) was of the view that, students life contexts, socio-cultural background and environment form the foundation for education. The curriculum of what the students are learning should therefore draw a lot from the students' environment and cultural background.

The instructional resources such as textbooks, and teaching aids should be rooted to the students' socio-cultural backgrounds. Recommended textbooks should be the ones written by indigenous scholars, and teaching aids should be drawn from the students' environment. Localizing instructional resources will make teaching and learning more real and appealing than when foreign

materials are used. Sometimes, renowned indigenous scholars and entrepreneurs can be invited as guest lecturers. Seeing such people from the same environment who are successful in life will motivate the students and bring the learning concepts closer than when foreign materials and human resources are used. This finding and discussion is supported by Bassey (2001), and Major and Leigha (2019).

The incorporation of indigenous research frameworks and community engagements are necessary considerations in decolonization of economics education. Indigenous research frameworks in economics education prioritize the perspectives, knowledge, and experiences of indigenous communities, their economic needs, values and culture through a holistic approach. Community engagement on the other hand requires involving local communities in deciding what and how economics is taught. It involves local communities partnering with universities; ensuring that students learn by solving local challenges, ensuring that local economic practices and traditions are added in the curriculum; and ensuring that curriculum reflects local economic realities and needs. All these will enhance sustainable creativity through the expression of ideas and innovations that will be profitable to the community members now and in future. This finding and discussion is supported by Adebayo (2018) and Onyekwelu (2020).

Decolonization of economics education for sustainable creativity and human capital development would require addressing some pedagogical issues. Teachers should be adequately trained on decolonization pedagogical strategies and continuous professional development programmes should be organized to close identified gaps. This according to Mavuru and Makhunga (2020) should include choice of teaching methods, utilization of instructional materials and

language of instructions. All these should be rooted to the students socio-cultural experiences and environment.

The study also revealed that, the challenges of decolonization of economics education for sustainable creativity and human capital development include: inability of curriculum planners to adequately contextualize economics education curriculum; shortage of qualified curriculum planners; inadequate infrastructure; poor funding of education; high influence of Western culture and technology; lack of political will; insufficient indigenous research framework; and inadequate training of teachers on economics education decolonization strategies. These findings are supported by Isa and Lawal (2023), Abiola and Samuel (2023), Ocho (2013) and Obiazamomwan (2024). Curriculum planners lack the capacity and ability to integrate IKS and contextualize economics education curriculum appropriately in a way that our socio-economic needs, culture, values, local economic practices and entrepreneurship are prioritized. This is worsened by the fact that we do not have enough trained and qualified curriculum planners in economics education.

Poor funding of public universities in Rivers State has caused a lot of setbacks in the educational system. It has affected infrastructural developments, recruitment and training of teachers, innovation and creativity, as well as over hauling the curriculum to integrate IKS and local practices to make our education system relevant to our socio-cultural, economic and technological needs. This situation is supported by lack of political will to promote decolonization of education by our policy makers and government authorities. They are rather promoting Western-centric curriculum due to over bearing influence of western culture and technology on us. They prefer anything western too anything that is locally originated.

Insufficient indigenous research framework affects decolonization of economics education. there is need to prioritize indigenous research to enhance the development of IKS, technology, and local economic practices to the benefit of the society, for sustainable creativity and human capital development. Government should ensure that teachers are adequately trained on curriculum decolonization strategies. This is necessary because inadequate skills on decolonization strategies can limit contextual relevance of economics education curriculum, it may also serve as a challenge to critical thinking due to lack of exposure to diverse economic perspectives, and it may consequently impact negatively on innovation and creativity as well as human capital development.

Conclusion

The study investigated decolonization of economics education for sustainable creativity and human capital development in public universities in Rivers State. Decolonization of economics education will be of immense benefit to the society because it will enhance the development of IKS, contextualization of economics education curriculum and the promotion of our socio-cultural heritage. It will also promote sustainable creativity and human capital development through an educational system that is eco-friendly or environmentally relevant, culturally relevant, and holistic in nature. It will make education more relevant to local contexts and result to the development of individuals with contextual skills and capacity to address local economic challenges in other to drive local development. Government should therefore pay adequate attention to decolonization of economics education due to its potential impact on sustainable creativity and human capital development.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the researcher made the following recommendations:

1. The curriculum of economics education should be adequately reviewed and contextualized, with indigenous knowledge, socio-economic practices and entrepreneurship well integrated into it.
2. Government should demonstrate the political will to decolonize some aspects of economics education programme by effectively implementing some policies aimed at promoting IKS, local economic practices and indigenous research frameworks.
3. Government should increase the budgetary allocation to education in order to allow educational institutions to tackle infrastructural deficits.
4. Government should ensure that economics education teachers are well trained on curriculum decolonization strategies.
5. Educators and students should value indigenous ideologies and knowledge system just as they value western ideologies, none of them should be seen as being inferior to the other.

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